

HΣPHÆSTUS

Heritage in EuroPe: new tecHnologies in crAft for
prEServing and innovaTing fUtureS

Project No. 101095123

Deliverable 5.3

Report on the digitisation process of craft museums

Funded by
the European Union

Document Control Page	
Project acronym	HEPHAESTUS
Project title	Heritage in EuroPe: New techNologies in crAft for prEServing and innovaTing fUtureS
Action	HORIZON EUROPE Culture, Creativity and Inclusive society
Duration	48 months
Grant no.	101095123
Work package	WP5 – Establishing Future Crafts Green Living Lab
Deliverable	Deliverable 5.3
Tasks	Task n. 5.3
Starting Date	01/11/2023
Due Date	30/05/2026
Submission Date	29/05/2026
Document type	Deliverable (D5.3)
Version	1.1
Dissemination level	Public
Abstract	<p>This deliverable examines how digital technologies mediate craft heritage across institutional and contemporary artistic contexts. It combines the digitisation of 512 objects from Palazzo Sturm in Bassano del Grappa with interviews with craft makers in Bornholm, including artists involved in the Sustainable Craft competition during the Craft and Kultur Uger. Using an ethnographic, multi-sited approach, the report shows that digital tools support preservation, access, and dissemination, while remaining closely shaped by material qualities, expert judgement, and embodied craft knowledge. The findings suggest that digitisation is best understood as a hybrid socio-material process in which heritage objects and contemporary craft are translated and reinterpreted across physical and digital environments.</p>
Keywords	Cultural heritage; craftsmanship; digitisation; digital technologies; materiality; heritage preservation; museum
Statement of originality	This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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Document History

Version	Date	Authors, reviewers, contributors	Changes
D5.3 v0.1	04/10/2025	Giulia Maragno	Structure proposal
D5.3 v0.2	01/03/2026	Giulia Maragno (CBS), Lea Jacobsen (CBS)	First draft
D5.3 v0.3	29/03/2026	Giulia Maragno (CBS), Lea Jacobsen (CBS), Simone Giotto (CDBG), Riccardo Taffanin (CDBG), Rebbie Preston (BOFA), In Kyong Lee (BOFA)	Second draft and revisions by partners
D5.3 v1.0	29/05/2026	Giulia Maragno (CBS), Lea Jacobsen (CBS), Simone Giotto (CDBG), Riccardo Taffanin (CDBG)	Final draft

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1. Executive Summary

This Deliverable 5.3 as part of the HEPHAESTUS project examines how digital technologies mediate the preservation, transmission, and transformation of craft heritage across two settings: the digitisation of museum objects at Palazzo Sturm in Bassano del Grappa while also drawing on interviews with Bornholm-based craft makers involved in the Craft Object competition to explore how digital tools are experienced in current practice. Taken together, these two strands demonstrate that digitisation while being a technical process, it is also a process in which digital tools, material qualities, and human expertise are closely intertwined across heritage preservation and craft making. In Bassano, the project supported the cataloguing and online dissemination of 512 selected ceramic objects, improving access (e.g. via Europeana) and long-term preservation, while also facing challenges while working within institutional, and operational constraints. In Bornholm, interviews with craft makers showed that digital tools can expand experimentation and communication, but they do not replace embodied skill or material knowledge. Across both contexts, the report concludes that craft heritage is best understood as something that is continually reworked through the interaction of analogue and digital practices.

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Acknowledgement

HEPHAESTUS project ID 101095123 is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

2. Purpose and structure of the report

The purpose of this report is to document and reflect, within Task 5.3, on how digital technologies mediate the preservation, transmission, and transformation of craft heritage in both institutional and artistic contexts. It starts from the premise that heritage is part of human experience (Sandford, 2019) and, as such, is inevitably entangled with the digital transformations reshaping our society. The report contributes to Objective 1 and 2 of the HEPHAESTUS project, namely, to analyze how craft processes and materials have become cultural heritage and to preserve craft heritage through digitisation.

Contrary to what was initially planned at the beginning of the project, and due to the ongoing renovations at Bornholm's Museums, Copenhagen Business School (CBS) and BOFA decided to shift the focus of the research not only towards institutional contexts, but also towards contemporary artistic practices, as crafting has always involved human interaction with technologies, whether pens or hammers in the past, or digital tools (Bunnell, 2004) in contemporary times.

In the institutional context, the study focuses on heritage digitisation practices at Palazzo Sturm in Bassano del Grappa (Italy). The aim here has been to examine the process through which cultural heritage is translated into digital form. In parallel, the research engaged contemporary artists who participated in the Sustainable Craft competition during the *Craft and Kultur Uger* in Bornholm (Denmark) over the course of the project, to understand their views and experiences regarding the use of digital technologies in their practices. By adopting this dual perspective, the research conducted within this Task aims to generate insights into the agency of digital tools and their entanglement with the materiality and of craft artefacts across institutional and artisanal contexts.

The report is structured as follows. It first introduces the project and the research focus. The following section develops the literature review, followed by the methodology and the illustration of the empirical contexts. The main body of the document then presents a comparative analysis of the two research sites. More specifically, it analyses the observations conducted during the fieldwork at Palazzo Sturm, where the CBS ethnographer followed the digitisation activities, together with the reflections emerging from

the interviews with craft makers in Bornholm regarding the use of digital technologies within contemporary craft practices.

3. Introduction

This report, Deliverable 5.3, presents the digitisation activities developed within Task 5.3 “Digitising craft heritage” of the HEPHAESTUS project, focusing on a selected collection of 512 art pieces from the partner museum, Palazzo Sturm (Bassano del Grappa, Italy). Moreover, it presents the reflections emerged from discussions with craft makers in Bornholm regarding the use of digital technologies within contemporary craft practices. The task is implemented under Work Package 5 and is led by Comune di Bassano del Grappa (CDBG), with the participation of BOFA and Copenhagen Business School (CBS).

The main objective of Task 5.3 is to support the digitisation of craft heritage objects through professional cataloguing and digital documentation, thereby enhancing accessibility, visibility, and long-term preservation of museum collections. The resulting digital catalogue (<https://www.museibassano.it/it/collezione/1882>) contributes to making cultural heritage available through the museums’ institutional platforms and through Europeana, fostering wider public engagement with craft traditions and material culture. Moreover, it will feed into Task 2.4, to inform the development of a methodology for the 3D scanning of heritage objects. At the time of writing this report, the upload of the artefacts (512 objects digitised) to the Europeana platform is still ongoing. Nevertheless, as illustrated in the Research Contexts section, the historical objects from Palazzo Sturm have already been uploaded to [Cultura Italia](#), the national aggregator and Europeana partner for Italian cultural heritage.

The digitisation activities were carried out in collaboration between a professional curator based at Palazzo Sturm and a multidisciplinary team, including an ethnographer from CBS, namely Giulia Maragno. While the curator is responsible for the technical processes of cataloguing and digitisation, the ethnographic contribution provides critical reflection on the broader implications of heritage digitisation practices, particularly in relation to the transformation of heritage artefacts into mediated digital objects. This work is primarily documented in this report and reflects such considerations and critical analysis. This

analytical dimension is further connected to the conceptual framework developed in Task 2.4.

The implementation of the Task 5.3, however, was affected by significant institutional, administrative, and operational delays (see also HEPHAESTUS Progress Report 2025 for more information). In Bornholm, activities were disrupted by the closure of Bornholm Kunstmuseum from October 2023 as part of a planned redevelopment into a larger museum complex. This process involved the removal and storage of collections, changes in staffing arrangements, and the temporary decommissioning of visitor areas. Although the redevelopment project was later cancelled in June 2024 due to rising construction costs, the subsequent reopening of the museum in July 2024 required a rapid reorientation of institutional priorities. Staff capacity was redirected towards reopening, exhibition planning, and internal reorganisation, which limited the museum's ability to formalise collaboration on digitisation within the HEPHAESTUS timeframe. This change was approved by the commission during the project review 2025.

At the same time, discussions within the consortium explored the possibility of expanding the original scope of the task from catalogue-based digitisation towards the 3D scanning of a selected group of artefacts. This alternative (in connection with UNIVE) was considered because of its potential to increase public engagement and to create more interactive forms of access to craft objects, techniques, materials, and practices. The proposal was also seen as potentially relevant to the project's broader work on digitisation protocols. However, following a change in the Project Officer, the consortium was instructed to adhere to the original Grant Agreement. This required a revised implementation strategy, aligned with the task as initially defined, while taking into account the changed operational realities in both museum contexts.

In Bassano del Grappa, further constraints emerged from the legal and professional requirements governing the digitisation of cultural heritage in Italy. The Comune di Bassano del Grappa (CDBG) had originally allocated resources to recruit external specialists, including a photographer and an external curator, since the Municipality does not have the necessary in-house professional profiles for this work. Italian cultural heritage regulations, including ICCD standards, require that documentation and cataloguing of heritage objects be carried out by individuals with appropriate certified expertise. These requirements are

essential to ensuring the quality, reliability, and institutional validity of the resulting catalogue records, but they also increased the administrative and financial complexity of the task.

As a result, the implementation of Deliverable 5.3 was revised. The digitisation work now focusses primarily on selected objects from Palazzo Sturm, where the museum had confirmed and fulfilled its commitment to supporting the practical conditions required for the work.

The cataloguing and photographic documentation as demonstrated in this report follows the relevant Italian legal and institutional framework, including Article 17 of Legislative Decree 42/2004 and the standards defined by the Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione under the Ministry of Culture. Photographic documentation complies with ICCD requirements concerning image format, resolution, file size, background, lighting, and framing. The use of qualified professionals is particularly important for the documentation of three-dimensional objects such as ceramics and other craft artefacts, where lighting, perspective, material texture, and object handling are central to the production of accurate and meaningful visual records.

Although the adjusted scope means that digitisation activities cannot be extended to Bornholm Museum in the manner initially envisaged, engagement with the Bornholm context has remained relevant to the Task. Activities related to Task 5.3 in Bornholm specifically concerned: 1. the documentation and investigation of contemporary craft practices on the island, with particular attention to their relationship with digital technologies; 2. the digital archiving and photographic recording of submissions to the annual Craft Object competition, which began in 2022; and the recording of newly crafted objects that may contribute to Bornholm's future craft tradition and cultural identity. In addition, the work involved collaboration with Bornholms Center for Kunsthåndværk, Makers Island, participating artists, and HEPHAESTUS project partners to support the preservation, interpretation, and public dissemination of Bornholm's evolving craft heritage.

Despite these delays and complications, the Task remains aligned with the overall objectives of HEPHAESTUS: to strengthen the preservation, accessibility, and public understanding of craft heritage, and to explore how digital tools can contribute to the continued relevance of craft knowledge in contemporary cultural contexts.

4. Setting the ground

Craft has been present in societies since prehistoric times, when people began creating simple objects through the entanglement of different materials and tools. Over time, some of these craft objects have acquired artistic status, either through their preservation in museums and cultural institutions as part of a specific heritage or through their emergence from contemporary artistic practices. “Craft” is thus a multifaceted concept, referring not only to objects, but also to actions, practices, and processes of making (Surette & Paterson, 2022).

This review thus attempts to trace the evolution of craftsmanship in both its tangible and intangible dimensions and, ultimately, to examine how these dimensions are reshaped by the spread of digital technologies, considered one of the defining phenomena of our time (Partarakis et al., 2025).

The review is organised into three interrelated sections. The first explores how historical craft objects moved from everyday use into museum collections and heritage institutions. The second considers how craft practices continue to inform contemporary art. Together, these sections address both the materiality of craft objects across past and present contexts and the immaterial dimension of craft as a living practice. The third section turns to the role of digital technologies in both the digitisation of craft objects held within museums and the emergence of digitally mediated forms of making within contemporary practices.

4.1. Craft objects as cultural heritage

Today, traditional craftsmanship includes a wide range of artefacts: tools, clothing and jewellery; objects used for storage, transport and shelter; decorative art and ritual objects; musical instruments and household utensils¹. This understanding applies both to historical craft objects and to contemporary artefacts.

While the next section will delve in depth into contemporary practices and artefacts, this one focuses on craft objects as material manifestations of tangible cultural heritage, connected

¹ For more information: <https://ich.unesco.org/en/traditional-craftsmanship-00057>

to the past while remaining embedded in the present. Many of these objects that once fulfilled practical functions and were embedded in everyday life (Seglow, 2018), gradually acquired significance beyond their utilitarian purposes, becoming valued also for the social and aesthetic worlds from which they emerged. As a result, these objects began to be collected and preserved to safeguard not only their material and functional characteristics, but also the sense of place and belonging they convey (Surette & Paterson, 2022), together with broader qualities of heritage and identity (MacDonald, 2021).

This transformation is closely tied to the institutional practices through which artefacts are collected, ordered, preserved, and exhibited (Bennett et al., 2017) within museums and cultural institutions. Through these practices, cultural institutions actively recontextualise craft objects as material testimonies of the stories of their makers, owners, and the societies in which they lived and continue to live (Surette & Paterson, 2022). In this way, craft objects acquire the status of heritage artefacts through the inscription of reconfigured values, structures and narratives (Smith, 2022), becoming part of broader constructions of memory and identity.

This institutionalisation of craft objects also transforms the relationship to their original contexts of use. Once relocated within exhibition spaces, artefacts become subject to curatorial and institutional practices that shape the creative, political, economic, and social meanings attributed to craft (Hart et al., 2022b).

4.2. Craft as a contemporary artistic practice

While some craft objects have been institutionalised as heritage, craft also persists as a living practice that shapes contemporary artistic production. In contemporary contexts, craftsmanship continues to inform artistic practices, distinguished by the “judgement, dexterity and care which the maker exercises” (Pye, 1968, p. 20) in the creation of objects. This section examines how craft has been theorised through materiality, embodied knowledge, skill, labour, and processes of making. In doing so, it approaches craft as a dynamic field of artistic production that crosses the boundaries of art, design, heritage, and everyday making.

Rather than focusing solely on the finished product, craft can be understood as a contemporary artistic practice where attention shifts from the finished object alone to the

process of making, the material engagement involved, and the meanings produced through that process (Adamson, 2007). From this perspective, craft also constitutes an important dimension of intangible cultural heritage, where material skill, process, labour, function, and tradition shape the meaning of the work itself (von Busch, 2022).

Historically, craft has been treated secondary to fine arts because of its association with manual labour, tradition, and function. However, it is important to note here that the boundaries between what is considered “art” and what is considered “craft” are often blurry and the terms are often used interchangeably. Shiner (2012) offers a broad account of contemporary debates on the blurred boundaries between art, craft, and design, arguing for a more nuanced understanding of craft that acknowledges its distinctiveness while also recognising its overlap with art and design, opening a richer and more inclusive view of craft. Hence, rather than treating craft as a fixed category, he suggests understanding it as unstable, hybrid and relational, moving between art, heritage, and contemporary practices.

Similarly, Adamson (2007) presents craft as a process, as an approach, an attitude and a mode of action. This perspective opposes the primary view on art which is usually oriented towards aesthetics and optical effects. Craft, in contrast, is organised around materials and the intensive engagement with them (Shiner, 2012), a dimension that is closely related to that of *skills* and the re-appropriation of the material world (Micelli, 2012).

Pöllänen (2013) further highlights the emotional aspects of craft and how craft as a practice contributes to well-being. The author views craft as a lived human experience, and not as a means to an end. In relation to this deliverable, this perspective is essential, because craft objects are shaped by both history and embodied processes. Niedderer and Townsend (2012) also support this view by focusing on the “essence of craft” as judgement, care, material engagement, and *thinking through making*.

This understanding is also shaped by the social and institutional contexts in which craft is displayed and interpreted. Hart et al. (2022a) argue that exhibitions, both for historical and contemporary craft objects, are key sites where the technical, social, political, and collective dimensions of craft are made visible, contested, and redefined. Craft, therefore, also depends on how objects are framed through curatorial practice and institutional display. Likewise, Prince's (2017) study of craft-artists in Bornholm shows how craft operates as a

situated artistic practice, shaped by local identity, tourism, livelihood, and the negotiation between artistic integrity and commercial demands.

4.3. Digitally mediating craft objects and practices

Digital technologies and their operations are increasingly embedded in human interactions with each other and with the world, becoming “mundane practices” (Just, 2025, p. 25). In this context, both museums preserving heritage artefacts and contemporary craft practices are increasingly shaped by digital technologies and their implications. Their use in the heritage sector therefore has multifaceted effects, both for artefacts preserved within museums and for the ways of working, making, and thinking associated with contemporary craft practices (Niedderer & Townsend, 2012).

Within museum contexts, “digital” can encompass a wide range of meanings and practices (Malde & Parry, 2018): i) digital as an artefact, a tool used to carry out certain activities; ii) digital as a process, therefore the strategies adopted to implement digital projects; iii) digital as the output of a creative process, namely the creation of digital products or content; iv) digital as the environment in which museums operate, shaping relationship with the public and, more broadly, with society. Together, these dimensions illustrate how digital technologies increasingly mediate the preservation, accessibility, and circulation of heritage artefacts (European Commission, 2024), allowing heritage to transcend physical and geographical boundaries. At the same time, digital technologies have specific affordances that enable different forms of action and interaction (Majchrzak, A & Markus, 2013). As recent studies have shown, digitisation can enable new services and forms of engagement, such as virtual exhibitions, digital catalogues, and research tools (Navarrete, 2019). Beyond these functional dimensions, the digital turn is also reshaping the practices by which artefacts are selected, ordered, and preserved (Kallinikos et al., 2013), while also transforming how digital and material cultures intersect and evolve (Rossi, 2019).

This transformation extends beyond museums and shapes contemporary craft practices. To craft something has always involved human interaction with technologies, whether pens, hammers, or digital tools, such as computer or software (Bunnell, 2004). If craft is understood not only as an object but also as a set of practices, digital technologies are becoming increasingly embedded in these living activities. On the one hand, this creates

new opportunities for experimentation and for the production of “unique, hybrid, individually designed forms” of expression (Bunnell, 2004, p. 3). On the other hand, the growing use of digital tools can transform relationships with materials, making engagement with them more visual and intellectualised (Shiner, 2012).

Digital technologies are thus not simply stand-alone tools, but agents deeply entangled in relationships with humans and their application contexts (Faraj et al., 2018), reflecting “our concerns, practices, our values and beliefs” (Introna, 2014, p. 44) shaping how historical and contemporary craft objects are preserved, produced, circulated, and experienced across both physical and digital environments.

5. Methodology

5.1. Research contexts

The research was conducted across two complementary craft contexts: Bassano del Grappa in Italy and Bornholm in Denmark. While Bassano, and specifically the ceramic museum at Palazzo Sturm, provides a context strongly connected to the preservation and digitisation of historical craft, Bornholm offers insight into contemporary craft practices and artistic production. Together, these contexts enable an exploration of how digital technologies mediate both the institutional preservation and transmission of heritage artefacts and contemporary processes of making.

5.1.1. Bassano context as a ceramic district

Bassano del Grappa has a long-standing ceramic tradition, supported by the presence of clay deposits in the hills along the banks of the Brenta River. The earliest documented evidence of ceramic production in Bassano dates to the mid-seventeenth century, with records of the Manardi factory. Between 1669 and 1719, the factory was granted a privilege by the Venetian Senate to produce maiolica across the entire territory of the Republic. It was particularly during the Eighteenth Century, within a highly favourable economic and cultural context, that the town expanded and emerged as a centre of significant European interest. This development was supported by its strategic location between the Venetian hinterland

and the commercial routes to Northern Europe, which facilitated an extensive network of exchanges.

This context fostered not only the circulation of goods but also the transfer of artistic models, production techniques, and skilled craftsmanship. Important ceramic manufactories were established and developed, most notably that of the Antonibon family, active in Nove, a locality closely connected to the Bassano production system (Leonardi & Pareschi, 2025). During the Nineteenth and Twentieth centuries, this was followed by the factories of Giovan Battista and Gaetano Marcon in Angarano, as well as those of Gaetano Bonato near Ponte Vecchio, Niccolò Chiminello, and Antonio and Raffaele Passarin.

Ceramic production in Bassano is distinguished by its technical quality and stylistic diversity, ranging from maiolica decorated with floral and naturalistic motifs to narrative scenes inspired by mythology or everyday life, as well as forms influenced by Eastern and Northern European models. This ability to absorb and reinterpret external models reflects the cultural openness of the district and its integration into wider European artistic networks. Ceramics were not only craft products but also cultural artefacts and expressions of heritage, symbolising status, sophistication, and both local and international patronage.

Museum history and purposes

Within this rich historical context, the [Civic Museum of Bassano del Grappa](#) is located. The Museum was established through donations by the naturalist Giambattista Brocchi in 1828 and opened to the public in 1840, in the former convent of San Francesco, bringing together natural history collections, the Civic Library, and the first nucleus of the Art Gallery. The Museum was founded with the aim of collecting, preserving, and enhancing the artistic and historical heritage of the city and its surrounding territory. Today, the Museum operates as a complex and multifaceted system that functions both as an exhibition venue and as a centre for research, documentation, and education. Its mission is structured around three main pillars: the safeguarding of cultural heritage; its enhancement through exhibitions, public programmes, and cultural activities; and its transmission to future generations through educational and innovative practices.

The initial core of the ceramic collections, comprising maiolica produced by the Antonibon manufactory, entered the Museum through a series of donations between 1919 and 1949

and was originally displayed on the ground floor of the Civic Museum. In 1992, the rapid expansion of the collection, driven by further acquisitions and donations, led to the establishment of a dedicated museum space within Palazzo Sturm (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Palazzo Sturm. Photo shared by the Museum.

This Eighteenth century palace is one of the city's most significant historic buildings and still preserves frescoes by Giorgio Anselmi (1765), as well as contemporary stucco decorations (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Museum Hall. Photo shared by the Museum.

The Museum continues to receive significant donations on an annual basis, reflecting the strong engagement of the local community in the enrichment of its collections. In parallel, it regularly hosts temporary exhibitions dedicated to prominent local and national artists, fostering a continuous dialogue with its permanent collections.

Museum institutional structure

The Civic Museums of Bassano del Grappa are organised as a distributed system across multiple sites that reflect the diversity of its collections. Among these, the Civic Museum, located within the San Francesco complex, represents the core of museum activities. An equally important role is played by Palazzo Sturm, which hosts two major museums closely linked to the economic history of the area: the Giovanni Roi Ceramics Museum and the Remondini Printing Museum.

The integration of Palazzo Sturm within the Civic Museum system requires coordinated management of human, financial, and scientific resources, as well as joint planning of exhibitions and cultural activities. This organisational model enables the enhancement of individual collections while maintaining a coherent vision of the museum. In particular, the Ceramics Museum represents a key reference point for the study and promotion of the local ceramic tradition. Its collection includes artefacts spanning a wide chronological and typological range, providing a comprehensive overview of the development of ceramic production in the Bassano area and its surrounding regions. The richness of the collections also results in frequent loan requests from other institutions, such as *Gallerie d'Italia* and the *Museo Internazionale delle Ceramiche* in Faenza, for temporary exhibitions, in which the Civic Museums of Bassano actively participate.

Since 2021, the Museum has followed a significant innovation pathway through the progressive digitisation of its collections. These initiatives respond to multiple needs: ensuring the long-term preservation of artworks through the creation of high-resolution digital copies, while also expanding access to cultural heritage through online platforms. Digitisation is thus part of a broader digital transformation strategy aimed at integrating advanced technological tools into the management, study and communication of the collections.

Aims of the digitisation and the history of the collection being digitised

The digitisation project of the ceramic collection, initiated within the HEPHAESTUS project, is part of this broader trajectory. The collection selected for digitisation resulted from a stratified acquisition process over time, including private donations, public acquisitions, and the recovery of dispersed materials. It constitutes a corpus of significant scientific value, documenting not only the stylistic and technical evolution of ceramics, but also the economic and social dynamics of the region.

The selection of objects for digitisation followed a rigorous methodological approach. First, the historical and artistic relevance of the artefacts was considered, prioritising objects that represent key phases in local and national ceramic production or that display particularly significant stylistic or technical features. Second, the state of conservation was considered, prioritising more fragile or deterioration-prone objects, for which digitisation also serves as a form of preventive conservation. A further criterion concerned typological representativeness, ensuring a balanced documentation of different categories of artefacts, from everyday tableware to decorative items, and from serial productions to unique pieces. These criteria were complemented by considerations related to accessibility and research value, with particular attention to objects of relevance for scholars, students, and the public, to maximise the project's impact in terms of knowledge dissemination and access.

The digitisation activities carried out by the Ceramic Museum are fully aligned with the strategic framework defined by the National Plan for the Digitisation of Cultural Heritage 2022–2026 (NPD)², representing its concrete implementation at the local level. The four core objectives of the NPD – i) preservation of original artefacts; ii) access and enhancement; iii) research and iv) recovery of previous digitisation campaigns – are reflected in the actions undertaken by the Musei Civici through the HEPHAESTUS project. These include the digital cataloguing of the ceramic collection, the online publication of images and metadata for individual objects, and the recovery of previously catalogued materials that had not yet been systematically managed.

² For more information: <https://bit.ly/NationalPlanforDigitisationofCulturalHeritage> and <https://digitallibrary.cultura.gov.it/il-piano/>

Regarding access and cultural inclusion, the online availability of the collections expands opportunities for engagement, particularly for communities that may face barriers in accessing institutional culture. Furthermore, by adhering to interoperability standards promoted by the NPD, the Museum aims to connect its data to national and European systems, positioning itself as an active node within a broader digital cultural ecosystem.

The digitised collection has been made accessible through the Museum's website and through its progressive integration into Europeana, with the aim of reaching both specialist and non-specialist audiences and supporting research as well as broader cultural engagement. The upload of the records to Europeana required several intermediate extractions and transfers between Palazzo Sturm, the cataloguing system used by the Civic Museum, and the European platform. From the Museum's cataloguing system, where the external cataloguer had uploaded the inventory and catalogue records together with the photographic images, the data first had to be extracted in XML format. Then, with the support of the head of Cultura Italia, the ICCD data aggregator for Europeana, the record data, including the images, were published on [Cultura Italia](#) (Figure 3) and subsequently sent to Europeana's METIS Sandbox, followed by a request for publication on the European platform. Although the process is still ongoing, it has enabled the Civic Museum to work closely with Cultura Italia and the ICCD, making the objects from the Bassano's ceramic collections available to the public.

Overall, this digitisation pathway complements other recent initiatives developed in the context of HEPHAESTUS which, although not directly funded by the project, were significantly informed by its framework. In particular, the related "DigitArt3D" Young Researcher project at Ca' Foscari University of Venice, funded through Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), supported the development of a virtual game installed at the Museum for six months. Using touchscreen interfaces and dedicated software, the game enabled visitors to explore craft heritage in an interactive way through a multimedia application developed within the HEPHAESTUS context. The game was also designed to engage younger audiences and foster their interest in, and appreciation of, the region's artisanal and artistic heritage.

Indice delle risorse

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Figure 3 – Screenshot of some of the art pieces published on Cultura Italia. Screenshot taken by the ethnographer from the Cultura Italia website: <https://www.culturaitalia.it/risorse/>

5.1.2. Bornholm as a contemporary craft ecosystem

Bornholm became the first island community in the world, and the first region in Europe, to receive the prestigious World Craft Region title from the World Crafts Council AISBL. This recognition reflects the island's craft traditions, strong community spirit, and internationally respected artisans working within ceramics, glass, textiles, metal, and wood. Over time, Bornholm has developed a vibrant ecosystem of museums, biennials, galleries, and educational opportunities that connect local craftsmanship with the global creative economy. Institutions such as the [Bornholm Center for Arts & Crafts](#) (Bornholms Center for Kunsthåndværk), [The Ceramic Factory & Museum](#) of Bornholm (Hjorths Fabrik og Bornholms Keramikmuseum), and [Bornholm Art Museum](#) (Bornholms Kunstmuseum) have helped position the island as an international centre for contemporary craft and cultural exchange. Today, Bornholm is recognised worldwide not only for the quality and aesthetics of its craftsmanship, but also for its innovative approach to sustaining and evolving traditional craft practices. In this sense, the Island represents a context in which craft operates simultaneously as cultural heritage, artistic practice and local economic activity.

Recognising the importance of preserving and promoting craft heritage through digitalisation, especially amidst the current challenges of accessing heritage craft objects

due to the relocation of Bornholm's Museum, Bornholm's Center for Arts and Crafts, in collaboration with HEPHAESTUS project partners, has taken steps to investigate contemporary craft practices and their potential engagement with digital technologies. The initiative also focused on recording newly crafted objects that may become part of the island's future craft tradition and cultural identity.

Digitally mediating contemporary practices and craft objects

Building on the understanding that digital technologies can preserve both the material and intangible aspects of craftsmanship while making craft heritage more accessible to wider audiences, Bornholm has chosen to digitally archive the submissions to the [Craft Object competition](#), an annual event that started in 2022. These contemporary craft objects represent current artistic and material practices on the island, and potential future heritage. By digitally documenting these works, Bornholm creates a record of emerging craft expressions and ensures that future generations can access, study, and understand how contemporary crafts contribute to the evolving identity of the island.

The Craft Object competition submissions are particularly important because they offer a unique reflection of Bornholm's contemporary craft culture from both local and public perspectives. Participation is limited to artists based on Bornholm, making the competition a strong representation of the island's active makers, materials, and artistic approaches. At the same time, the winning works are selected through public voting by visitors to Bornholm Centre for Arts and Crafts, allowing local and international audiences to directly influence which craft expressions are recognised and celebrated within the Island's craft ecosystem. In this way, the competition captures not only what makers on Bornholm create, but also how these works are perceived, valued, and remembered by the public.

The competition has evolved through continuous collaboration and dialogue between participating artists, Makers Island, Bornholms Center for Kunsthåndværk, and the HEPHAESTUS project partners. Each year, the structure, themes, and practical frameworks of the program are adjusted to better support and strengthen the Island's craft sector and cultural practices. As a result, the submitted works reflect the individual artistic expression, and an ongoing collective process of shaping new traditions and identities within Bornholm's craft community. The competition has generated significant public engagement and interest,

empowering audiences to become active contributors to the development and preservation of Bornholm’s evolving craft heritage.

5.2. Data collection

This report draws on ethnographic methods, combining observation and interviews, with the aim of tracing analytical connections across the two research sites (Hine, 2007). In particular, ethnography is used not only as a method, but as a conceptual lens focused on practices (Hjorth et al., 2019) (see also D1.1 for information on HEPHAESTUS craft mapping methodology). Specifically, the fieldwork conducted in Bassano provides insights into the institutional preservation and digitisation of historical craft objects, while Bornholm offers a context in which craft continues to operate as a living and evolving practice. In both sites, the research was approached with flexibility, openness, relational depth, and sensitivity to context (Ingold, 2014), allowing attention to both institutional processes and everyday interactions surrounding craft objects and practices.

5.2.1. Observations

In the first research site, a preliminary meeting was conducted with the project manager of the Bassano Municipality, who responsible for coordinating and implementing the HEPHAESTUS activities related to the Task and for communication between institutional and external actors. The meeting help to gather a better understanding of the institutional context and the actors involved. Then, the museum curator shared documents and materials related to the history of the museum, the collection, and the list of objects selected for digitisation, enabling an initial understanding of the site and of the activities carried out within the specific Task.

Due to the museum’s internal organisation and activities, the fieldwork was conducted over the first week of February 2026. During this period, the museum was closed to the public to facilitate the movement and coordination of the professionals involved in the digitisation process. Alongside the museum curator, the digitisation activities involved a team from an external company responsible for handling and moving the artefacts from display cabinets and storage areas, custodians who supported access to storage and exhibition areas, an external photographer and an external curator responsible for uploading information on to the digitised objects to the museum’s website. The museum director supervised the

activities. Table 1 provides an overview of the human and non-human actors involved in the activities observed during the fieldwork.

<i>Human and non-human actors</i>	<i>Role in the digitisation practices</i>	<i>Interaction with artefacts and technologies</i>
Project Manager	Coordinated the HEPHAESTUS activities related to the Task and communication between institutional and external actors	Managed communication and organisational coordination throughout the digitisation process
Museum Director	Provided strategic supervision of the digitisation activities and institutional coordination	Contributed to the initial definition of the list of objects selected for digitisation, together with the museum curator
Museum Curator	Supervised the collection, selected artefacts, and coordinated the activities of the external company within the museum	Mediated access to the collection and revised the list of objects selected for digitisation
External Curator	Managed cataloguing and uploaded information on digitised artefacts to the museum website	Revised the list of selected objects and contributed historical and artistic knowledge about the artefacts
Custodians	Supported access, logistics, and movement within museum spaces	Facilitated access to storage and exhibition areas and supported the movement of heritage objects during photographic documentation
External Company Team	Handled, moved, and prepared artefacts for digitisation	Managed the physical movement and positioning of heritage artefacts during the digitisation process
Photographer	Carried out the photographic documentation of the artefacts	Produced high-resolution digital images of the collection
Craft artefacts	Heritage objects undergoing digitisation	Material objects around which the digitisation practices were organised
Digital technologies and equipment	Tools and infrastructures supporting the digitisation process	Enabled the photographic documentation, cataloguing, storage, circulation, and online accessibility of heritage artefacts

Table 1 – Human and non-human actors involved in digitisation activities at Palazzo Sturm.

Throughout the week, the ethnographer from Copenhagen Business School remained on-site during the museum's opening hours, acknowledging that her presence shaped the field, just as the field shaped the research process and methods adopted, which therefore remained flexible and combined different techniques (Hjorth et al., 2019). In addition to observations, informal conversations were conducted with the museum curator, the photographer, the custodians and the external curator, and manually recorded in the

researcher's notebook. A semi-structured interview with the museum director was conducted at the end of the week.

During these exchanges, particular attention was given to the different stages of the digitisation activities, including the rationales guiding the selection of objects, their removal from display cabinets and storage areas, the revision of the digitisation lists, the preparation and positioning of artefacts, and the photographic documentation of the collection. This enabled the researcher to observe the interactions emerging between professionals, heritage artefacts, and digital technologies (Cochoy et al., 2019).

Throughout the fieldwork, observational notes were taken to document reflections and observations related to the digitisation activities. These notes were initially written in Italian in a notebook and later transcribed in English into digital format using OneNote. Visual documentation also formed part of the ethnographic process, with more than 150 photographs taken to document the digitisation activities, the spatial organisation of the museum environment ([Figure 4](#)) and the photography laboratory.

Figure 4 – Spatial organisation of the museum environment. Photos taken by the ethnographer during the fieldwork in February 2026.

5.2.2. Interviews

In Bornholm, interviews represented the primary method of data collection. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with craft makers participating in the most recent editions of the Craft Object competition, held between 2023 and 2025. The choice to interview these artists, rather than the HEPHAESTUS ambassadors (although one participant was also a project ambassador), was motivated by the aim of collecting a plurality of perspectives and experiences. This multiplicity was also enriched by the fact that the craft makers involved worked with different materials and demonstrated heterogeneous forms of engagement with digital technologies, as summarised in Table 2. The interviews focused on participants' views and experiences regarding the role of digital technologies in their practices. Regardless of whether participants currently used such tools, the interviews explored how digital technologies shape, or may potentially shape, their engagement with materials, knowledge, and creative processes.

Participants were also invited to reflect on how digital technologies mediate the transmission of their work, as well as on the opportunities and risks that such mediation may entail for the preservation and communication of craft heritage to future generations.

Craftmaker	Primary material	Relationship with digital technologies	Examples of digital engagement
1	Wood	Experimental	3D modelling
2	Stoneware and porcelain	Integrated	Digital editing of texts and images using Photoshop prior to printing
3	Glass	Not used	No use of digital technologies in the artistic practice
4	Wood	Limited	Computer Numerical Control (CNC), Computer drawing, Laser branding machine
5	Ceramic	Limited	AI-assisted modelling

Table 2 – Overview of the craft makers.

Each interview lasted approximately 45 minutes and was conducted in English. With participants' consent, the interviews were audio-recorded and subsequently transcribed digitally using the software Konch. One of the craft makers did not consent to audio recording; in this case, the ethnographer manually documented the main points of the interview through written notes. The process of contacting, arranging, and conducting

interviews was carried out in close collaboration with BOFA, with care and respect for the participating craft makers, with particular attention given to valuing their time, energy, and working conditions. Participation in the interviews was entirely voluntary, and artists were informed in advance to allow sufficient time for consideration and scheduling.

In addition, the interviewer accommodated each participant's preferred location and timing to create a flexible and respectful interview environment that aligned with the realities of artistic and craft-based practices. With the exception of one participant, who is currently studying at the Royal Danish Academy in Copenhagen, all interviews were conducted in Bornholm in the craft makers' workshops. The interview with the participant based at the Royal Danish Academy took place in Copenhagen, followed by a walk through the Academy's making spaces. These visits enabled a situated engagement with the working environments of the craft makers and allowed observation of the tools, materials, spatial organisation, and creative processes involved in craft production, as well as the ways in which digital technologies were, or were not, integrated into everyday making practices. Overall, these visits made visible the everyday dimensions of craft practices and contributed to a broader understanding of craft as an embodied, situated, and material practice (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – Craft makers' workshops in Bornholm. Photos taken by the ethnographer during the fieldwork in March 2026.

5.3. Data analysis

To explore the entanglement between the human and non-human actors involved in the digitisation activities and in the use of digital technologies in everyday practices, the analysis adopted a Science and Technology Studies (STS)-informed perspective. More specifically, it drew on the idea that human and non-human actors come into being, interact, and perform realities together (Law, 2008), thereby shaping the practices in which they participate. In this sense, digital technologies were not treated as neutral tools, but as systems of knowledge and practice that both shape and are shaped by the tools they encompasses (Beyes et al., 2022), generating drifts, openings and translations (Flyverbom, 2019; Latour & Venn, 2002) that affect the preservation, circulation, production, and interpretation of craft heritage. Following (Surette & Paterson, 2022), agency was understood as distributed across craft makers, materials, making practices, technologies, and craft objects themselves.

The analysis therefore focused not on isolated actors, but on the relationships and interactions emerging between them. Particular attention was also paid to the material and relational dimensions of craft objects, which were approached as entities with specific life cycles shaped, at different stages, through interactions with digital technologies.

Across both research sites, the ethnographer conducted a preliminary analysis during data collection, recording key concepts and observations in field notes (Emerson et al., 2011). For each site, these initial reflections informed the identification of emerging themes to be explored further during the fieldwork and in the subsequent analytical process, while also supporting the gradual organisation and interpretation of the collected material (Neyland, 2008). The analysis of fieldnotes and interview transcripts was first conducted within each research site and then extended through a cross-site comparison aimed at tracing analytical connections between Bassano and Bornholm.

6. Results

The results presented in this report indicate that, across the two research sites and despite the differences between the institutional setting of Bassano and the contemporary craft practices in Bornholm, digital technologies are not external additions to existing practices, but become increasingly entangled with institutional routines, creative work, and the

materiality of craft objects. The results are organised in four parts, which examine digital technologies as mediators, their role in shaping hybrid practices, the relevance of materiality, and their implications for the visibility and accessibility of craft objects.

6.1. Digital technologies as mediators

Across both research sites, digital technologies emerged as active mediators embedded in broader socio-material practices, rather than as neutral tools supporting heritage preservation or craft practices in a purely technical way.

In Bassano, the digitisation of heritage artefacts was not an automated and purely technical operation, but a negotiated socio-material process through which heritage artefacts were translated into digital representations. The process required continual coordination among objects, technologies, materials, and the humans involved. Once heritage artefacts were brought into the photographic laboratory by the external company team and the custodians, the digitisation process unfolded through the photographer's ongoing interactions with a range of technical and digital elements, including a camera, a computer, lighting systems, and photographic panels. The production of digital images therefore depended on the ongoing alignment between the artefacts, the lighting conditions, the technologies, and the photographer's professional expertise. Mounted on an adjustable support, the camera could be repositioned according to the object being photographed, while the lighting was incrementally adjusted and recalibrated depending on the surface, material, and specific features of each artefact (Figure 6). The work around the objects required continuous small adjustments before each image could be produced. As the photographer explained while taking a picture, *"it is not simply a matter of positioning the light and taking a photograph. Each object is treated as a case in itself, responding to light in a particular way"*. He also noted that the digital images he was producing remained *"to some extent, his own interpretation"*.

The process therefore required a constant negotiation between the technical image production and the situated interpretation of the photographer, whose embodied knowledge contributed to digital representations that corresponded as closely as possible to the physical artefacts.

Figure 6 – Photographic laboratory set up in the spaces of Palazzo Sturm. Photos taken by the ethnographer during the fieldwork in February 2026.

Similar dynamics emerged in Bornholm through conversations with craft makers, where digital technologies were described as tools that mediate design and material production rather than replacing established craft practices. Craft Maker 1 framed digital technologies as part of a longer historical continuity of technological change, noting that *“for craft, I don’t think it’s actually an issue, because it’s just transitioning way of practice”*.

Reflecting more broadly, he also remarked that “*if you go back to the stone age, even a handsaw would probably be like ‘wow, that’s advanced technology’*”, suggesting that digital technologies are perceived less as a rupture with traditional craft practices than as part of their continuous transformation. Within these practices, digital tools enabled artists to visualise, test, and translate ideas into material forms in new ways.

This emerged also in Craft Maker 5’s reflections on her experimentation with AI-based modelling tools to generate a prototype for a ceramic cup. As she explained:

“I thought, okay, I might as well try some of these AI, 3D programs. So, I tried to describe what the cup looked like to get the program to make it. Oh my God, that was a lot of fun, and it was so disgusting what came out. I was really trying to explain it to the detail of how it was supposed to look, but that was very difficult. I didn’t try feeding it with a drawing. I could have drawn it and showed that. Because it said, do you want to give me text or images? So, at that moment, I couldn’t draw anything, so I was just trying to describe it. For what I could see that I tried to do what I wanted to, but it was not close at all”.

Taken together, the evidence from the two sites shows that digital mediation is constitutive of how heritage artefacts and craft practices are organised through digital and material relations.

6.2. Hybrid practices

Evidence from Bornholm shows how digital technologies are incorporated into craft practice through hybrid combinations of technical tools, embodied expertise, and material judgement. While digital tools became progressively integrated into making practices and material experimentation, they were not perceived as capable of replacing the embodied knowledge developed through craft makers experience. Reflecting on the 3D printers he was experimenting with (Figure 7), Craft Maker 1 explained that “*the newer technology gives you more possibilities and options to explore unconventional shapes or designs. But it also has its own limitations*”. Although 3D printing enabled the exploration of forms that would otherwise be difficult to achieve through traditional techniques, the craft maker stressed that “*the level of the finished quality is not up to deliverable stage*”, requiring continued handwork expertise to refine and complete the objects produced through digital tools. This reflection emerged again later in the interview, when the Craft Maker noted that “*the fine detail [...] is*

still hard to achieve with robots or 3D printing. But that's where also the humanistic touch comes in, makes a difference".

Figure 7 – 3D printers at the Royal Danish Academy. Photos taken by the ethnographer during the interview in March 2026.

This combination of different ways of working, together with the complementarity between human knowledge and digital tools, was also echoed by Craft Maker 3. Although she did not directly employ digital technologies within her own practice, she explained that she did not “*think it’s going to harm the craft to implement new technologies, because I think creative minds will always explore new ways of working and combining ways of working*”. Rather than replacing traditional craft practices, digital technologies were therefore perceived as becoming integrated into broader processes of creativity and experimentation. A similar perspective emerged also in the reflections of Craft Maker 2, who explained that he decided to introduce digital tools into his practices not to break with craft tradition, but to renew existing practices and create something new, “*something that would endure*”. In his work, a specialised printer capable of printing iron oxide was integrated into broader material processes involving clay and firing techniques, rather than replacing them.

Across the interviews, another recurring aspect concerned the time and the learning process required to incorporate digital technologies into existing craft practices. Craft Maker 1 described the experience of engaging with new technologies as learning to “*speak a new language*”, reflecting both the opportunities and discomfort associated with that.

At the same time, Craft Maker 3 and Craft Maker 5 both emphasised that integrating digital technologies into their work requires time. More specifically, Craft Maker 3 explained that she sees *“the potential of the 3D printing. I’m just not patient enough to kind of sit down and use the time to master the whole 3D programming and all that”*. And Craft Maker 5 echoed that: *“I could actually see myself using it in idea development. And then I could also see it being used in some mold-making. If I was casting something then if I could get it printed, I could also imagine printing directly in clay. Could be quite fun. So, it’s not that I’m have any aversion towards digital technology. It’s not at all. Actually, I would really love to do it because I think it’s fun. But it’s also a matter of time and priorities”*.

Although hybridity emerged more explicitly in the conversations with the craft makers in Bornholm, similar combinations of embodied expertise and digital technologies were also visible in the digitisation activities observed at Palazzo Sturm. During one informal conversation, the external curator highlighted how, for each object uploaded online, information had to be added *“as a kind of assemblage”*, in which *“for each object and each collection, a history must be condensed and reconstructed”*. He further argued that catalogue records should be accompanied by something resembling a *“cultural anthropology”*, where information is added to the object itself, complementing the image with layers of cultural and historical knowledge that contribute to shaping its presence within the digital environment (Figure 8).

Informazioni tecniche	
Autore	Bonaldi Federico
Titolo	Villaggio globale
Datazione	2004
Materia e Tecnica	Materiale refrattario Modellatura a colombino legno metallo
Misure	Larghezza 27 cm Profondità 16,5 cm Altezza 60 cm
Acquisizione	Donazione 2015 Famiglia Bonaldi
Inventario	C 2525
Collocazione	Palazzo Sturm

Figure 8 – Digital record of one of the historical objects digitised at Palazzo Sturm. Screenshot taken by the ethnographer from the museum’s website: https://www.museibassano.it/it/dettaglio_opera/859762.

Taken together, these observations suggest that hybridity is not simply the coexistence of analogue and digital elements, but rather a negotiated reconfiguration of knowledge, judgement, material work, and digital mediation.

6.3. Relevance of materiality

A key finding emerged across both research sites concerns the active role of materials in shaping interactions with digital technologies. In Bassano, the material properties of historical artefacts directly influenced the digitisation process, while in Bornholm the features of different materials shaped how craft makers adopted digital tools within their practices.

During the third day of field work in Bassano, the photographer remarked that heritage objects “*should be read*”. He explained that modern ceramics tend to have an opaquer surface, whereas older ceramics are often glossier. This difference affected the photographic process, as reflective surfaces could produce highlights that risk “*burning out*” the form of the object in the image. In a similar way, during another photographic sessions, the custodian brought over a chalice that the photographer decided to capture from both sides, explaining that a complete catalogue record would require multiple views of the object. While the first image was taken without difficulty, the second appeared slightly crooked once the chalice was turned around (Figure 9). When asked about the reasons of this irregularity, the photographer explained that it derived from the object itself: given the material and the way it was made, slight unevenness is common.

Figure 9 – Digitisation process of the chalice. Photos taken by the ethnographer during fieldwork in February 2026.

A similar situation emerged a few days later, with a series of tiles that presents slight irregularities (Figure 10). In both cases, rather than correcting or eliminating these imperfections through digital post-production, the photographer accepted the images as representations of the objects.

Figure 10 – Material irregularities in the tiles. Photos taken by the ethnographer during fieldwork in February 2026 and screenshot from the museum's website: https://www.museibassano.it/it/dettaglio_opera/866222.

Similar engagements between materials and digital technologies emerged in Bornholm. During the interviews with the craft makers, a recurring theme concerned the need to remain attentive to the material properties of objects while experimenting with digital tools and progressively learning how these technologies interact with different materials. As Craft Maker 1 explained, digital designs may appear convincing in virtual form, yet *“there will be more corrections or alterations with this technology (= 3D modelling), but it doesn't have much material knowledge implemented into this design”*. While digital modelling allows the creation of complex and visually appealing forms, the craft maker stressed that, once translated into physical objects, these designs may become *“too weak or too fragile”*, revealing the limits of digital tools when detached from embodied material knowledge.

In a similar way, Craft Maker 4 highlighted how, by using digital tools and specifically the CNC, he *“can just cut around shape wood a lot easier and faster, but also make square shapes and drill holes. (...) So, you can make a more advanced project”*, but, at the same time, he *“wants to show what's in the wood, and wants to take the features in there and actually expose them. And that's not really a thing you can do that with a 3D printer”*.

In contemporary practices, this engagement between materials and digital tools operates at different levels. As Craft Maker 5 explained, during a glaze course she attended participants were asked to use AI-based tools to generate the recipe for their ideal glaze: *“you describe what your dream glaze looks like. And then ChatGPT will give you a recipe. And then you go home and you try it. Some of the participants did it, and some of the glazes came out okay. And some of these were not close to what I was looking for”*. In recalling this episode, she acknowledged that AI-based tools are becoming *“wiser and wiser”*, but she also reflected on the gap between computational generation, and the material knowledge required to translate digital suggestions into workable craft outcomes.

Across both research sites, the findings suggest that digital technologies do not replace material engagement. Rather, materials shape how digital tools are used, interpreted, and incorporated into both heritage digitisation and contemporary craft practices.

6.4. Visibility and accessibility

Lastly, across both research sites, attention was also given to how digital technologies contribute to making historical and contemporary craft objects visible and accessible, both for public audiences and for the craft makers themselves.

In the museum context, visibility and accessibility were already shaped at the beginning of the digitisation process through the curatorial selection of the objects to be included in the digital catalogue. During the interview with the museum director, she explained how the selection of the historical objects ranged from early sixteenth-century pieces to twentieth-century ceramics. The aim, she noted, was to *“provide a representative overview of these 400 years of history, through the most significant pieces but also through a variety of objects that can convey the different typologies and decorative styles, and how these changed over time”*. Thus, the definition of the list of the objects to be digitised sought to give visibility not only to the collection itself, but also to the historical and cultural specificities of the territory. This selective process became particularly visible during a visit to the museum exhibition rooms with the internal and external curators, when discussions emerged regarding which objects should be added to the list for digitisation. For instance, the external curator suggested including two plates (Figure 11), explaining that although *“at first sight they may seem banal, the shaded component they possess is particularly interesting”*.

He further noted that these objects were historically significant because, during the nineteenth century, airbrush technologies were not yet available, making these decorative techniques especially relevant for understanding local ceramic production.

Figure 11 – Plate displayed at Palazzo Sturm. Screenshot taken by the ethnographer from the museum's website: https://www.museibassano.it/it/dettaglio_opera/848926

Similar attention was given to a plate connected to the aesthetic influence of Gio Ponti, considered important as testimony to the different ways of working that characterised the area (Figure 12).

Figure 12 – Plate displayed at Palazzo Sturm. Screenshot taken by the ethnographer from the museum's website: https://www.museibassano.it/it/dettaglio_opera/868548

Moreover, while discussing the process of making collections available online, the external curator reflected on how digitisation represents one of the ways through which museums and cultural institutions attempt to make their collections accessible. He described this process as a form of discovery that “*allows people to travel*”. A similar perspective was also expressed by the museum director, who stated that “*digitisation should not be understood as a substitute for the visit, but rather as a support – perhaps even as an initial invitation*” to the museum.

At the same time, however, the external curator also questioned the actual usability of the cataloguing system. In the specific case of the Bassano collection, he explained that, out of the 400 works selected for digitisation, only around 150 would receive expanded catalogue entries (Figure 13), while the remaining objects would be documented through more inventory-like records.

MBA		
OPERA	INFORMAZIONI TECNICHE	RICHIESTA IMMAGINI
<p style="text-align: center;">Volpato Giovanni (1735/1803) <i>Trionfo di Bacco e Arianna</i></p> <p>Il sontuoso centrotavola fu commissionato nel 1786 dall'ambasciatore veneto della Serenissima a Roma, Pietro Donà, a Giovanni Volpato. Giunto nella capitale nel 1771, il noto artista bassanese affiancò alla sua attività di incisore quella di antiquario e mercante d'arte e in seguito, a partire dal 1785, quella di ceramista, introducendo per primo in città la produzione di raffinati biscuit tratti dall'antico. Il centrotavola, ultimato nel 1788, ha come soggetto principale il "Trionfo di Bacco e Arianna" (inventario C 1371). Il fastoso corteo è accompagnato da due gruppi, uno con "Fauno con putto e capra" (C 1387) e l'altro con "Putti che giocano con la capra Amaltea" (C 1386), assieme ad una coppia di Baccanti danzanti (C 1381, C 1382) e una di Fauni (C 1384, C 1385), quattro "Puttini con maschere teatrali" su piedistalli (C 1388, C 1389, C 1390, C 1391), i due "Puttini Borghese" (C 1444, C 1445) e la riproduzione dell'Apollo citaredo con le nove Muse (C 1383, C 1372, C 1373, C 1374, C 1375, C 1376, C 1377, C 1378, C 1379, C 1380). A decorazione dell'intero dessert vi sono poi otto erme legate assieme da ghirlande floreali (C 1411, C 1412, C 1413, C 1414, C 1415, C 1416, C 1417, C 1418, C 1419), diciotto piccoli vasi su piedistalli (C 1392, C 1393, C 1394, C 1395, C 1396, C 1397, C 1398, C 1399, C 1400, C 1401, C 1402, C 1403, C 1404, C 1405, C 1406, C 1407, C 1408, C 1409), ventiquattro cammei con ritratti maschili e femminili tratti da originali antichi (C 1420, C 1421, C 1422, C 1423, C 1424, C 1425, C 1426, C 1427, C 1428, C 1429, C 1430, C 1431, C 1432, C 1433, C 1434, C 1435, C 1436, C 1437, C 1438, C 1439, C 1440, C 1441, C 1442, C 1443), oltre a ventuno pilastri con catenelle di metallo (C 1446, C 1447, C 1448, C 1449, C 1450, C 1451, C 1452, C 1453, C 1454, C 1455, C 1456, C 1457, C 1458, C 1459, C 1460, C 1461, C 1462, C 1463, C 1464, C 1465, C 1466). È probabile che il corteo sia stato suggerito a Volpato dal celebre affresco con il Trionfo di Bacco e Arianna dipinto da Annibale Carracci nella volta di Palazzo Farnese a Roma, ma sicuramente, ad ispirare l'opera fu ancora di più il soffitto dipinto dall'amico Antonio Zucchi, marito della pittrice Angelica Kauffmann, nella biblioteca di Newby Hall, residenza del noto collezionista di antichità inglese William Weddell.</p>		

Informazioni tecniche		
	Autore	Volpato Giovanni (1735/1803)
	Titolo	Trionfo di Bacco e Arianna
	Datazione	1786 - 1788
	Materia e Tecnica	Biscuit
	Misure	Altezza 34 cm Larghezza 42 cm Profondità 40 cm
	Acquisizione	Dono 2000 Associazione degli Amici dei Musei e dei Monumenti di Bassano del Grappa
	Inventario	C 1371
	Collocazione	Palazzo Sturm

Figure 13 – Digital record of one of the historical objects digitised at Palazzo Sturm. Screenshot taken by the ethnographer from the museum’s website: https://www.museibassano.it/it/dettaglio_opera/849264

Although emerging in different ways, a similar tension between digital visibility and material presence also appeared in Bornholm through the conversations with the craft makers.

Craft Maker 1 emphasised the importance of embodied engagement with craft objects, explaining that “*I value the physical object more than being a digital. I have no problem that being on a digital exhibition. But I would say I would value more having and seeing and touching a physical object*”. In contrast, Craft Maker 5 reflected on how digital images increasingly become central to the circulation and visibility of her objects, stating that “*the picture is more important to me than the actual piece. Because the piece might be sold to somebody, and then it’s sitting there in their living room, and if I lose the picture, then I’m like, okay, I can’t show this piece anymore to anyone*”. In this case, she highlights that the digital image functions not simply as documentation, but as a way of preserving the accessibility of the work after its physical circulation into private spaces. A similar attention to visibility and preservation also emerged within the broader Bornholm craft ecosystem through the activities of Bornholms Center for Kunsthåndværk, which is currently reflecting on how to digitally document and archive both contemporary craft practices and the objects exhibited during the Craft Object competition (Figure 14 and Figure 15) in a sustainable way over the long term. In this sense, digitisation aims to contribute not only to increasing accessibility, but also to preserving contemporary craft objects as potential future heritage.

Figure 14 - Photos shared by Bornholms Center for Kunsthåndværk. Photo by Kasper Agergaard depicting artworks by participants in the Craft Object competition.

Figure 15 – Photos shared by Bornholms Center for Kunsthåndværk. Photo by Kasper Agergaard depicting artworks by participants in the Craft Object competition.

Evidence from the two sites shows how digital technologies reshape the visibility and accessibility of craft objects, while also revealing the selective character of digital circulation.

7. Concluding remarks

This report has presented an empirically grounded and analytically informed account of the role of digital technologies in two different, but connected, settings: the digitisation of craft heritage held within a museum, namely Palazzo Sturm in Bassano, and the use of digital tools within contemporary craft practices in Bornholm. The multi-sited comparison has shown that digital technologies do not simply add a technical dimension to heritage management and craft production. Rather, they become deeply entangled with the material and immaterial aspects of craft, thus objects, materials, expertise, and creative practices, actively shaping them.

In Bassano, the digitisation of a selection of the Museum's collection showed that the development of the digital catalogue depends on the coordinated work of curators, photographer(s), custodians, external specialists, as well as digital tools and infrastructures, and the material features of the artefacts themselves. The digitisation of heritage artefacts was both a challenge for the Museum, given the number and fragility of the selected objects, and an opportunity to expand and refine knowledge of the collection and connect it more clearly to the cultural identity of the territory and its European dimension.

In Bornholm, the interviews with craft makers shed light on how digital technologies are being incorporated into contemporary craft practices in ways that reflect the longer history of technological change that has shaped craft practices over time. For some craft makers, digital tools opened new possibilities for experimentation, design, circulation, and communication; for others, they remained limited to specific phases of the making practice or were not used at all. Across these varied experiences, however, a common pattern emerged: digital tools did not displace embodied knowledge, material sensitivity, or human refinement, but they became part of hybrid practices in which craft makers negotiated the extent to which digital technologies could support, extend or alter their work.

Across both settings, the report has also discussed the centrality of the material features of historical and contemporary craft objects. Whether photographing a ceramic artefact or

experimenting with digital fabrication, the work remained shaped by the resistance, texture, surface of the materials. This reinforces the fact that digitisation is deeply entangled with craft objects, emerging as a process through which materiality is reframed, translated, and made available in new ways.

Finally, the report also highlights the importance of accessibility and transmission. In Bassano, digitisation expanded the possibility of sharing the collection more widely; in Bornholm, digital mediation offered craft makers additional means of documenting, communicating, and potentially preserving their work for future generations. Yet, what becomes accessible through digital means is the output of selective processes, shaped by technical possibilities but also interpretive decisions.

Taken together, the findings show that considerations related to the use of digital technologies in both institutional and contemporary craft contexts is not a matter of choosing between analogue and digital forms, but to recognise that these forms coexist and mutually transform one another. This points to the importance of approaching digitalisation not as a purely technical process, but as a socio-material transformation that intervenes in heritage objects at different moments of their life cycles: in the museum context, once they have already been made, preserved, and selected for documentation; and in the craft context, while they are being designed and brought into form.

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